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Publisher's Living Handbook for Diamond Open Access

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Abstract	This Deliverable outlines the conceptualisation and implementation of the Publisher's Living Handbook for Diamond Open Access (Living Handbook) as a result of the CRAFT-OA project. The Living Handbook is a digital reference resource that supports self-learning user-experience. It provides user-specific results developed within CRAFT-OA for journal editors, technical staff, and institutional publishers, making them freely available. The term "living" in the context of a Living Handbook indicates that it allows for ongoing additions, updates and corrections. The Living Handbook was developed in collaboration with Communities of Practice (CoPs) and has been aligned with DIAMAS results. The Living Handbook is integrated in the EDCH and available under https://handbook.diamas.org .

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List of Acronyms

CAP	Common Access Point
CoP	Community of Practice / Communities of Practice
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DISCO	Discoverability Companion
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
ePUB	Electronic Publication
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FHH/SUBHH	Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg/Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Hamburg
FOSS	Free and Open-Source Software
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
ID	Identifier

IPSP	Institutional Publishing Service Providers
IPTHL	Institutional Publishing Technical Living Handbook
IPTP	Institutional Publishing Tool & Technology Providers
JATS	Journal Article Tag Suite
KER	Key Exploitable Result
Living Handbook	Publisher's Living Handbook for Diamond Open Access
LMS	Learning Management System
LTS	Long Term Support
MU	Masarykova Univerzita
NCC	National Capacity Centre
OA	Open Access
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OJS	Open Journal Systems
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OS	Open Science
PDF	Portable Document Format
PHP	Hypertext Preprocessor

PID	Persistent Identifier
RFO	Research Funding Organisations
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SeDOA	Service Centre for Diamond Open Access (Servicestelle für Diamond Open Access)
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
TLS	Transport Layer Security
UGOE	Georg-August-Universität Göttingen
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Publisher's Living Handbook for Diamond Open Access (OA) is a key outcome of the CRAFT-OA project. The Living Handbook is a reference work providing user-oriented access to project results. Its primary objective is to strengthen the technical empowerment of Communities of Practice (CoPs) engaged in Diamond OA publishing. As one of the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs), the Living Handbook is designed to serve as a sustainable, continuously updated resource that will remain active beyond the project's duration.

As a digital user-oriented platform, the Living Handbook systematically organises and provides access to CRAFT-OA outputs, including tools, guidelines and training materials. Its design aligns with CRAFT-OA's broader objectives of enhancing technical infrastructure, fostering professionalisation through capacity building, and improving the visibility and discoverability of Diamond OA publications. As a reference work, its content is curated and reviewed by experts.

Central to the concept is its "living" nature. The Living Handbook is a dynamic, evolving resource that can incorporate new materials, updates, and corrections in response to ongoing developments in the field. This adaptability was reflected in the project's development process. Its design was guided by a flexible working framework, enabling continual adjustments as the project progressed. Regular community feedback played a decisive role in shaping the concept and functionality at multiple stages.

Sustainability was a high priority during planning and implementation. The project developed a technically sustainable solution taking the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) principles¹ into account. Collaboration with the Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication (DIAMAS) project further strengthens the sustainability. The Living Handbook is available as a subdomain of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) and forms part of the EDCH's service portfolio.

A toolkit for editors will support ongoing editorial work beyond the project's lifecycle. The editorial sustainability of the Living Handbook will be supported by an international Editorial Board comprising members from European National Capacity Centres (NCCs) involved in Diamond OA publishing. The German NCC, Service Centre for Diamond Open Access (SeDOA), has confirmed its participation on the board and its ongoing support for the Living Handbook.

¹ GoFAIR Initiative, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

2 INTRODUCTION

The CRAFT-OA project aims to consolidate the Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing landscape. This objective is realised through technical improvements for various Communities of Practice (CoP) and by fostering overall infrastructure development. The outcomes of the CRAFT-OA project are made available in a central reference resource, presented as a living handbook.

The Publisher's Living Handbook for Diamond OA (Living Handbook) aims to support the technical empowerment of CoP within the field of Diamond OA publishing. Identified as one of the Key Exploitable Results (KER) of CRAFT-OA, the Living Handbook is designed to be a sustainable source that will be maintained and updated after the project ends.

3 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The Living Handbook is a digital resource designed to document and provide structured access to the outputs of the CRAFT-OA project. It makes relevant project results such as tools, guidelines, and training materials available in a user-oriented and systematically organised format.

The aims and objectives of the Living Handbook are aligned with the overarching goals of the CRAFT-OA project, which include strengthening technical infrastructure, supporting professionalisation through capacity building, and increasing the visibility and discoverability of Diamond OA publishing.²

The main objectives of the Living Handbook are:

- To centralise access to practical technical resources produced within the CRAFT-OA project;
- To offer a sustainable framework that can be updated and maintained beyond the project timeline;
- To support technical capacity building by presenting structured, clearly described information for defined user groups;
- To foster the implementation of shared standards aligned with the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS)³ and CRAFT-OA Deliverable 3.1 Report on Standards for Best Publishing Practices and Basic Technical Requirements in the Light of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) Principles.⁴

The Living Handbook is a specific type of publication. Handbooks are types of reference work or collections of instruction intended to provide ready reference. To provide reliable information, references require content that has been reviewed by experts and is of a high quality.

The term “living” in the context of a Living Handbook indicates that it is a dynamic and continuously updated work of reference. It allows for ongoing additions, updates and corrections to reflect the latest discussions. In essence, a “living” handbook is never considered a finished work but continues to evolve.

² CRAFT-OA (n.d.). CRAFT-OA – Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access. Retrieved November 27, 2025, from <https://www.craft-oa.eu/>.

³ Consortium of the DIAMAS project (2025). The Diamond OA Standard (DOAS). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15227981>.

⁴ CRAFT-OA Deliverable 3.1, Report on Standards for Best Publishing Practices and Basic Technical Requirements in the Light of FAIR Principles. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112662>

4 METHODOLOGY

The development of the Living Handbook is rooted in conceptual openness, adaptability, and community participation. From the outset, both the content and structure of the Handbook evolved in line with project outcomes, user needs, and collaboration.

As the Living Handbook is a compilation of project outcomes, the timing of these results' creation influenced its development. As most outputs emerged gradually, the Living Handbook, as a meta-result, could only be structured once the underlying materials existed. The wishes and needs of the target groups also needed to be taken into account. This meant that a decision regarding the technical implementation had to be made at a later stage of the project. Accordingly, a flexible working framework was drafted to allow for adjustments as the project progressed. Throughout the project, community feedback was sought on several occasions, influencing the status of the concept at each stage. In this respect, the concept, and therefore the development of the Living Handbook, correspond to the "living" nature of the result itself.

4.1 Target Groups

CRAFT-OA addresses a broad range of stakeholders within the Diamond OA ecosystem. The Living Handbook is specifically designed to reflect the needs of these CoPs, ensuring relevance and accessibility.

4.1.1 Core Target Groups

Based on the CRAFT-OA stakeholder analysis in Deliverable D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan⁵, the following groups are defined as primary users:

- Diamond OA journals: Editors, authors, and reviewers operating either independently or within Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs). Their experience ranges from beginner to advanced, requiring differentiated support and training.
- (IPSPs: Institutional units providing infrastructure and support for Diamond OA journals.
- Institutional Publishing Tool & Technology Providers (IPTPs): Institutions offering the technical environments and infrastructure for OA publishing.

⁵ Arasteh-Roodsary, S. et al. (2023). CRAFT-OA Deliverable 7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112795>

- Technical staff: Developers and maintainers of software tools and services that support Diamond OA workflows.

These groups form the foundation of the CoPs addressed by the Living Handbook. Their needs define its content strategy and pedagogical approach.

4.1.2 Further Target Groups

Additional stakeholders are addressed indirectly, in particular with regard to cross-cutting issues such as governance, funding, and policy development:

- Funders: Support Diamond OA initiatives financially and contribute to their sustainability.
- Decision-makers: Develop institutional and national strategies that frame the conditions for Diamond OA.
- Citizen scientists and principal investigators (PIs): Engage in open and participatory research, requiring accessible publishing pathways.
- Research libraries: Facilitate OA publishing, develop infrastructures, and serve as knowledge hubs.

4.1.3 Requirements of Core Target Groups

The core target groups were merged to specific user roles, namely “Journal Editors,” “Technical Staff,” and “Publishers.” This facilitates user-oriented content navigation and enhances the usability of the Living Handbook. To cater to varying experience levels and use cases, the Living Handbook implements a tiered content structure for these roles. This approach allows users to access content suited to their expertise and role in the publication process. It also offers tailored navigation pathways to ensure that content is accessible and actionable.

4.2 Community Feedback

The incorporation of community feedback on an equal footing was a key aspect of the methodology. Even though CRAFT-OA team members belong to different CoPs, it is crucial to involve users as specific representatives of CoPs in product development when creating a service for them. As representatives of the target groups, users offer valuable practical insights. This community participation ensures the creation of a truly community-driven product: for the community, with the community, by the community.

The core target groups were actively engaged in shaping, managing, and developing the Living Handbook by directly inviting them to several events. CRAFT-OA organised

four major events (see below). All were used to work directly with the target groups to develop and adapt the concept of the Living Handbook. A different focus was addressed on each occasion.

The Living Handbook's fundamental structural considerations and its initial content focus are based on feedback gathered during the **1st CRAFT-OA Summer School in Telč** (Czech Republic, May 2024), including surveys and polls.⁶ A collaborative workshop was conducted with representatives of the core target groups. These activities helped to define the target groups as well as user roles. They also highlighted the need for the Living Handbook to have a structure that accommodates different levels of prior knowledge and allows navigation by role, activity, and product.

The outcome was the design of a navigation architecture that provides multiple access vectors to the Living Handbook. Users can retrieve content by role, workflow activity, or product category, and can perform keyword-based browsing. This instructional architecture supports operational implementation and optimises long-term usability and maintainability.

A dedicated session at the **CRAFT-OA Tech Event in Torino** (Italy, October 2024) gathered feedback on the implementation of these results and further developments. This was followed by a discussion regarding the next steps with the participants, among whom were journal editors, tech staff and publishers.

The **2nd CRAFT-OA Summer School in Coimbra** (Portugal, July 2025) coincided with the launch of the first version of the Living Handbook. During a workshop at the event, representatives from the target groups provided initial feedback on the website. The workshop focused on collaboratively designing editorial workflows and ensuring sustainability. The resulting feedback was incorporated into the Toolkit for Editors.⁷

At the **CRAFT-OA Conference – “Crafting the Future of Diamond Open Access: Technical, Social & Political Perspectives of Scholarly Publishing”** in Göttingen (Germany, October 2025), further discussions on editorial sustainability took place. During the course of the project, the National Capacity Centres (NCCs) were identified as crucial for editorial sustainability. At the meeting of the NCC Network, coordinated by the EDCH, the idea of an Editorial Board comprising NCC members was proposed and discussed positively.

⁶ Greiner, I. (2024). Evaluation of Community Feedback from the 1st CRAFT-OA Summer School for Journal Editors in Telč (CZ) 2024. CRAFT-OA Summer School for Journal Editors, Masaryk University Center, Telč (CZ). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14222114>

⁷ See [A2.2 Editorial Workflow](#).

4.3 Renaming

During the course of the project, it became apparent that the name “Institutional Publishing Technical Living Handbook” (IPTHL), as referenced in the Grant Agreement, was too long and unwieldy for practical communication and everyday use. However, the short form “Living Handbook,” as it became established in daily use, can only serve as an abbreviation due to its lack of informative value.

The Living Handbook's primary objective is to support communities, with a strong emphasis on usability. The original name fails to reflect its wider scope of content and intended user base. In particular, independent journal editors, i.e., those who publish solely on their own account, should explicitly be included. The new title also highlights the “diamond” aspect, which is essential both to CRAFT-OA and to the Living Handbook. Changing the Living Handbook's name was therefore an appropriate and necessary step to ensure its relevance, usability and sustainability. This is emphasised by the fact that renaming it was suggested by the community, and that the modified name was well-received within the project. The name “Publisher's Handbook for Diamond Open Access” was put to a vote among the project partners and, following the advice of the EU expert, expanded to include the term “living”.

4.4 Content Acquisition

4.4.1 Content Identification

To support content organisation, a dedicated content-audience spreadsheet was developed. The tool mapped project outputs to specific user groups and use cases, helping to align structural decisions with actual needs. Feedback from the community during the 1st Summer School was taken into account when selecting user-specific content and identifying project results with direct benefits for users.⁸ This approach provided a foundation for designing an accessible, user-centred system.

⁸ Greiner (2024).

4.4.2 Templates⁹

To ensure the systematic and consistent integration of project outputs into the Living Handbook, a set of standardised templates was developed for content collection. These templates were designed to gather essential metadata and descriptive information about each outcome in a structured manner.

One template covers results defined as deliverables and milestones, respectively, and another addresses training materials. Both templates were developed based on those from the Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication (DIAMAS) Toolsuite.¹⁰ The DIAMAS Vocabulary, created for the DIAMAS Guidelines,¹¹ became an integral part of the Living Handbook's keyword system. This approach contributes to the standardisation of EDCH services and supports their sustainability.¹²

Additional metadata is required to improve content description and to extend search and filtering capabilities. The metadata schema also references areas of activity as defined in the CRAFT-OA Reusable Curriculum for Upskilling Trainings on Diamond OA Standards and Technologies.¹³ This Curriculum provides a modular framework for upskilling qualification in technical topics and takes into account the variety of publishing environments in which they occur. It is designed to support upskilling across different expertise levels. Users of the Reusable Curriculum can locate training materials in the Living Handbook that correspond to – and are mapped against – the Curriculum's framework.

Initial versions of the templates were tested within the core group working on the Living Handbook. Following internal feedback and refinements, a final version of the general content template was released. In addition, a specially modified version of the template was created for training-related outcomes. This training-specific template was developed in close consultation with the responsible task leaders and subsequently approved for use.

All templates and related entries were centrally collected and documented using Confluence. To ensure broad engagement, the communication strategy for distributing the templates followed a multi-channel approach:

⁹ See [A2.4 Templates for Content Description](#)

¹⁰ Armengou, C., et al. (2024). DIAMAS Deliverable D4.3 – IPSP Guidelines (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13786094>

¹¹ Armengou, C., et al. (2024). DIAMAS Deliverable D4.2 IPSP Toolsuite. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14001342>

¹² <https://diamas.org>

¹³ Kupreyev, M., Fenner, J., & Müller, L. (2024). CRAFT-OA Deliverable 2.2 Reusable curriculum for upskilling trainings (Draft.). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10943284>

- All task leaders responsible for relevant project outcomes were contacted via email and instructed to complete the individually prepared templates associated with their deliverables.
- The importance and process of content collection were communicated in several work package meetings.
- Participants who had conducted or created training activities were additionally contacted and asked to use the training-specific template.

To monitor the collection process and ensure transparency, a dedicated spreadsheet for outcomes was created. This spreadsheet documented the submission status of each template and tracked completed, pending, or missing entries. Reminder emails were sent to contributors for missing or incomplete entries.

In order to reference the outcomes of CRAFT-OA and to make them accessible to users, a description and an explanation of their benefits was required to highlight their added value. This was achieved through entries in the Living Handbook which systematically reference the project's outcomes. The finalised templates were edited by a small core team and used to generate texts presenting the results of CRAFT-OA and illustrating their value to the relevant target groups.

This coordinated and structured acquisition process established the foundation for the Living Handbook as a consistent, searchable, and user-oriented knowledge base that captures the outputs of CRAFT-OA and supports their long-term reuse. The systematic approach to content acquisition, combined with the use of standardised templates, enhances the scalability and sustainability of the Living Handbook.

4.5 Cross-Project Exchange with DIAMAS

Throughout the project, forward-looking agreements regarding product development and direction were established with the DIAMAS¹⁴ project. CRAFT-OA initiated a mutual exchange to stay aligned with the development of the DIAMAS Common Access Point (CAP), which later evolved into the EDCH. The goal was to identify overlaps and synergies while avoiding redundancy. Sustainability was the guiding principle in these discussions.

As a result, DIAMAS templates and vocabulary were adopted. The integration of the Living Handbook into the CAP was discussed, and CRAFT-OA, together with DIAMAS partners, decided to integrate it as a subdomain of the EDCH.¹⁵ DIAMAS was involved in the Living Handbook's software selection process, and the planned integration into the EDCH naturally influenced its design scheme. These coordination efforts

¹⁴ DIAMAS, <https://diamasproject.eu/>

¹⁵ See [5.2 Hosting](#)

continued after the end of the DIAMAS project, ensuring that the Living Handbook aligns with EDCH services.

The Living Handbook participates in the EDCH Tools and Technologies Task Force.¹⁶ This task force deals with technical excellence and aims to foster collaboration within the Diamond OA community in order to support sustainability and innovation for the future.

The measures discussed support the seamless integration of the Living Handbook as a complementary facet of the EDCH portfolio.

¹⁶ <https://diamas.org/task-forces>

5 CONTENT OF THE LIVING HANDBOOK

The Living Handbook provides user-specific outcomes from the CRAFT-OA project. The term “user-specific” refers to results that are directly relevant to the roles of “Journal Editor”, “Technical Staff”, or Publisher”. These results aim to enhance users’ skills, provide training materials, and support the improvement of infrastructures for Diamond OA publishing. This includes outcomes such as project deliverables and milestones, such as information on plugins,¹⁷ services¹⁸, and other aspects of Diamond OA publishing infrastructure. Toolkits¹⁹ and training materials support users in applying CRAFT-OA outcomes in practice. In line with the project’s open approach and to promote and strengthen knowledge sharing within the Diamond OA community, all content is freely accessible and reusable. All Living Handbook content is provided under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.²⁰ Referenced content is required to be licensed under an open license.

To highlight its user-orientation, the following use case illustrates the specific problems addressed by the Living Handbook and how users can find relevant content. These examples illustrate the purpose and functionality of the Living Handbook, helping communicate its structure and value to different target groups.

For example, journal editors often struggle with the inconsistent requirements of indexing services. A tool referenced in the Living Handbook – the Discoverability Companion (DISCO) plugin – offers targeted support. DISCO consolidates indexing criteria from major databases into a self-assessment tool integrated into Open Journal Systems (OJS).²¹ Editors can filter by role (“journal editor”) to find the entry, which includes the plugin, documentation, and related resources. This helps editorial teams to streamline their indexing efforts, improve discoverability, and reduce their administrative workload. Thanks to the navigation structure which offers multiple pathways, DISCO can also be accessed, for example, via the activity “Work with OJS or Comparable Systems” or the “Tool” category. The plugin can also be found by searching for keywords such as “Software Code (PHP, XML)” or “Discoverability”.

This flexible approach reflects the community’s emphasis on the need for multiple entry points when searching for or browsing specific content.

This use case shows that the Living Handbook is more than a collection of project results. It is structured around real user needs. Through the combination of role-

¹⁷ Discoverability companion (DISCO)

¹⁸ Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH), <https://ddh.diamas.org>

¹⁹ Diamond Open Access Starter toolKit (Do.ASK)

²⁰ See <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

²¹ Gomola, R., Dvořáková, M., Gingold, A., & Cuel Oller, N. (2024). *Discoverability Companion (DISCO) plugin*. GitHub. <https://github.com/munipress/disco>

based navigation and other user-oriented navigation approaches, the handbook enables context-sensitive, practical use.

5.1 Structuring the Content

The structure of the Living Handbook, i.e. the user-interface design, depended on various factors that could not be fully anticipated at the time it was conceptualised. These factors include:

- The amount of information provided internally about the project outcomes.
- Ongoing coordination with other interested projects (e.g. DIAMAS) that have their own communication concepts.
- Requirements from ongoing processes in other parts of the project, for example the work packages on the sustainability of the project results.
- Changing user expectations.

Structuring the content in the Living Handbook benefits users by enabling them to locate specific product types, identify guidance related to publication-process activities, or access content tailored to their role or target group. These discovery pathways are combined and implemented at multiple levels, using different methods to ensure flexible and efficient content navigation. Accordingly, the content is organised along three primary dimensions: (1) target groups, (2) publication activities, and (3) product types.

5.1.1 Content Structure According to Target Groups

The target groups have already been defined. One way to ensure an intuitive user experience in the Living Handbook is to guide users according to their specific roles and provide targeted content recommendations. By identifying their respective roles and requirements, users can be directed to information most relevant to them. This structure supports orientation and promotes user-centred navigation. Content is therefore grouped and tagged to ensure discoverability by the roles “Journal Editor,” “Technical Staff,” and “Publisher”.

5.1.2 Content Structure according to Publication Activities

The target groups have needs arising directly from their publishing activities. The project outputs are structured by assigning them to typical activities of the target groups. Users who need help with a specific publication activity can thus find targeted support. The outputs in the Living Handbook are organised in such a way that they are presented and can be found in connection with the following activities and needs.

- Working with OJS and comparable systems that support publication workflows is a significant focus of both the target group of the Living Handbook and the project. This activity can therefore serve as a natural link. Relevant content in the Living Handbook is tagged especially for those involved with OJS and similar systems.
- Creating Visibility: Many of the outputs developed in CRAFT-OA are aimed at creating visibility for publications. These include technical products such as plugins, but also guides and standards. Those looking to increase the visibility of their publication organs or publications can find or access ways to do so in the Living Handbook.
- Network and Communicate: Several outputs reinforce the concept of networking within the CoPs, highlighting ways to provide mutual support. This can be further enabled through technical infrastructure that itself embodies a networked structure.

5.1.3 Content structure according to product groups

Users might search for specific product groups. Targeting the content according to specific product groups is therefore another way of structuring the content of the Living Handbook.

- Tools: This section provides access to various software tools developed within the CRAFT-OA project. Users can find descriptions that support the use and better understanding of these tools, as well as links to additional resources assisting with their application in different contexts.
- Training Materials: In this section, users can access a range of training materials focused on technical processes and best practices. The materials offer guidance and practical instructions, equipping users with the knowledge and skills needed to apply these practices effectively.
- Reports: Here, users find comprehensive guidance on ways to improve publishing workflows according to Diamond OA requirements. This section contains reports and experiences which different users can adapt to their own purposes.

Further sections may be considered according to communities' future needs.

5.2 Content Navigation

The organisation of content through a user-centered interface is implemented via a combination of measures. Navigation is built around an intuitive menu, which incorporates visual elements that provide access to content depending on the previously defined structure. The elements are distinguished from each other by shades of the same base colour. Supplementary I-messages within the menu enhance clarity and encourage solution-oriented interaction by framing content from

the user's perspective. These messages guide users to identify themselves ("I am"), express their goals ("I want"), or stimulate motivation and curiosity ("I am looking for"). Interactive buttons incorporate subtle gamification elements to further engage users.

Figure 1: This screenshot shows the intuitive entry points on the Living Handbook's home page.

After selecting a navigation path, content corresponding to that choice is displayed on a dashboard. A subsequent click allows the user to access the selected reference entry.

Another way to find content of specific interest is to search the complete collection to discover all available content by using one or more keywords or to browse through all displayed entries.

Figure 2: This screenshot illustrates the available browsing options on the Living Handbook's home page.

Further navigation options are available at the level of individual entries. These include linked tags (keywords) that refer to corresponding entries, and the option to search for content relating to specific user groups, key actions or products from each entry

6 TECHNICAL DESIGN

In line with other DIAMAS services and CRAFT-OA KER such as the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH),²² the Living Handbook is integrated into the EDCH as a subdomain (<https://handbook.diamas.org>). It uses Moodle in order to meet the technical requirements for advanced search functionalities and a user-centred presentation of search results. At the same time, the chosen software solution aims to support a user-friendly content structure, in line with the structuring approaches outlined in Section 4.

6.1 Platform: Requirements and Evaluation

The decision for a particular platform software was made after content had been acquired. This was based on the decision to align the technical solution with the requirements of content and its presentation, not the other way round. However, the range of technical solutions available was limited from the outset by the requirement that the selected solution should largely meet the FAIR criteria. In addition, the Report on Standards for Best Publishing Practices and Basic Technical Requirements in the Light of FAIR Principles²³ was used as the basis for a differentiated assessment. These criteria include the possibility of integrating global identifiers (IDs), the accessibility of metadata, as well as the existence of controlled vocabularies, open licenses and community support to ensure sustainability. Based on this analysis, two platform solutions were shortlisted: Drupal and Moodle. Both were also summarised in a SWOT analysis²⁴ that served as a basis for further decision-making.

Moodle was selected due to its modular architecture, user-friendliness, and adaptability to various user roles. The decision for Moodle was driven by the need to provide a platform capable of supporting both structured documentation and potential training elements within a cohesive environment. As a Learning Management System (LMS), Moodle provides the capability to enhance reference entries using H5P elements, including presentations, interactive videos, and quizzes. The fact that Drupal has already been successfully used in DIAMAS spoke in its favour, so that an integration of the information services of both projects (see next chapter) would be a strong argument in favour of Drupal. In the end Moodle proved particularly convincing due to its low-threshold implementation, interactive content features, and strong suitability for the didactic aims of the Living Handbook. In addition, Moodle allows for the quick and flexible deployment of content.

²² <https://ddh.diamas.org>

²³ Armengou, C. et al. (2025). CRAFT-OA Deliverable 3.1 Report on Standards for Best Publishing Practices and Basic Technical Requirements in the Light of FAIR Principles (Final). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14637597>

²⁴ See [A4 SWOT Analyses for the Use of Software for the Living Handbook](#) in the appendix.

To promote overall usability, the platform generally supports multilingual content and enables editorial workflows adapted to different user roles.

6.2 Hosting

Decisions regarding the hosting of the *Living Handbook* are closely linked to considerations regarding its long-term sustainability. Integrating the Living Handbook into an external information service whose operation is secured beyond the duration of the project will significantly facilitate the maintenance and further development of its technical infrastructure.

6.2.1 Verification of Technical Integration into the EDCH

In light of this, CRAFT-OA has explored potential collaboration with the EDCH. Initial considerations for integrating the Living Handbook into the EDCH were shaped by a series of joint meetings between the EDCH team and CRAFT-OA. To assess whether the Living Handbook's requirements could be met within the EDCH infrastructure, an implementation plan was developed. The aim was to keep the option open to integrate the Living Handbook into Drupal. However, it became clear during the course of the project that the specific requirements of the Living Handbook could not be fully met using Drupal. Following an in-depth and long-term evaluation within the CRAFT-OA project, the decision was made to implement the Living Handbook in Moodle. This choice addresses the need for user-friendliness, advanced search functionalities, and didactic flexibility. Accordingly, the *Living Handbook* is implemented as a technically independent instance in Moodle, but conceptually and visually closely aligned with the EDCH through integration as a subdomain. This approach ensures clear affiliation while preserving the Living Handbook's editorial and structural autonomy. This solution offers the advantage of a close connection to the EDCH while maintaining operational flexibility within CRAFT-OA.

6.2.2 Cooperation with a Subcontractor

To maintain the technical infrastructure of the Living Handbook, the service is implemented by commissioning the service provider lern.link²⁵ (a Moodle Premium Certified Partner). The subcontractor acts as a host on behalf of the FHH/SUBHH. He operates the Living Handbook on a shared server, managing its technical support and maintenance. Data management is ensured to be General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliant. Regular updates and related adjustments are performed, alongside daily data backups, ensuring consistent operation and data security. The technical implementation of the Living Handbook is carried out with as

²⁵ <https://lern.link/>

few adjustments as necessary and is largely standardised in order to make maintenance and security as sustainable as possible. Thus, the Living Handbook can be easily migrated to another subcontractor if necessary.

6.3 Visual Design

The visual design of the Living Handbook is created in line with the EDCH Design Manual²⁶ in order to provide a smooth integration into the EDCH. It aims to provide a clear and user-friendly interface that facilitates intuitive access to content for all users. A central aspect of the design is the visual differentiation of content for different user groups. This may be achieved through the use of colour schemes, icons, or other visual markers, helping users to quickly orient themselves based on their role or experience level.

The interface follows responsive design principles, ensuring optimal usability on both desktop and mobile devices. The layout and structural logic of the handbook is consistent across all sections to foster familiarity and reduce cognitive load.

Navigation is supported by clear visual elements, and filter functions that allow users to understand their position within the handbook at all times and move fluidly between sections. The overall aesthetic follows a minimalist approach to keep the focus on content and readability.

Clarity and a minimalistic design further enhance the accessibility of the Living Handbook. Moodle has been accredited as compliant with Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.2 standards. To support the widest accessibility possible, software customisation is kept to a minimum.

²⁶ <https://diamas.org/communication-kit>

7 SUSTAINABILITY²⁷

The sustainability of the Living Handbook is anchored within the Diamond OA community, ensuring long-term viability and expansion. Technical sustainability is provided by the SUBHH (Hamburg State and University Library). To maintain the technical infrastructure of the Living Handbook, it is implemented using the LMS Moodle in cooperation with the service provider lern.link (a Moodle Premium Certified Partner). Moodle is a free Open Source software package. The software is developed and supported by a large international community. The subcontractor will handle hosting through October 2027. The Living Handbook is operated on shared servers, managing its technical support and maintenance. Regular updates and related adjustments are performed, alongside daily data backups, ensuring consistent operation and data security. The technical implementation of the Living Handbook is carried out with as few adjustments as necessary and is largely standardised in order to make maintenance and security as sustainable as possible. Thus, the Living Handbook can be easily migrated to another subcontractor if necessary.

Moreover, the Living Handbook is scalable in terms of capacity and scope, enabling it to grow and adapt over time. It is publicly available as a subdomain of diamas.org and is therefore a dynamic component of the EDCH.

The editorial sustainability of the Living Handbook is to be supported by an international editorial board, comprising members from European NCCs engaged in Diamond OA publishing. Discussions with NCCs are ongoing to identify individual representatives from their networks to join the editorial board, ensuring that the editorial direction and further structural development of the Handbook lie in the hands of the European Diamond OA community. The Editorial Board will be mainly responsible for conceptual development and expansion of content.

The German NCC, Service Centre for Diamond Open Access (SeDOA), has confirmed its participation in the editorial board and its ongoing support for the Living Handbook. As part of its commitment, SeDOA will also work to build its own knowledge base based on the structure and principles of the Living Handbook. Currently, SeDOA is exploring the integration of its knowledge base into the platform, a step that would serve as a model for other NCCs, further enhancing the sustainability and adaptability of the Diamond OA ecosystem. FHH/SUBHH is both KER owner for the Living Handbook and responsible for the knowledge base in SeDOA. This offers potential for synergies for the Living Handbook.

²⁷ See Holsinger, S. et al. (2025). CRAFT-OA D7.7 Update: Exploitation and Sustainability Plan.

This collaborative model enables the Living Handbook to highlight country-specific topics, fostering greater equity in the dissemination of knowledge and enhancing visibility for localised contributions to the Diamond OA movement. Initially, the core version of the Living Handbook will feature reference entries solely in English, with future provisions to support content in other European languages.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10943284>

Laakso, M., Edig, X. van, Fenner, J., Armengou, C., Gingold, A., Pispiringas, L., & Šterbenc Svetina, B. (2024). CRAFT-OA Deliverable 3.2: Report on challenges and help measures faced by OA journals and platforms. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10496594>

8.2 List of Websites

CRAFT-OA <https://www.craft-oa.eu/>

DIAMAS <https://diamasproject.eu/>

Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH) <https://ddh.diamas.org>

EDCH <https://diamas.org>

GoFAIR Initiative <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

SeDOA <https://diamond-open-access.de/>

9 LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: This screenshot shows the intuitive entry points on the Living Handbook's home page.	22
Figure 2: This screenshot illustrates the available browsing options on the Living Handbook's home page.	22

10 APPENDIX

A1 Technical Specifications of the Living Handbook

The Living Handbook is implemented using the LMS Moodle in cooperation with the service provider lern.link²⁸ (a Moodle Premium Certified Services Partner).

A1.1 Technical Specifications

Technical aspect	Description
Uniform Resource Locator (URL) (Home page)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● https://handbook.diamas.org <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ subdomain of EDCH
Moodle version	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 4.5.7
Script	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Hypertext Preprocessor (PHP)
Server location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Nürnberg, Germany Backup Server Locations: Nürnberg and Falkenstein, Germany
Server type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Linux server ● Installed, maintained and administrated by lern.link exclusively ● Server shared with other lern.link platforms
Theme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Boost Union
Colour scheme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EDCH Design Manual
Access restrictions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No geographical restrictions ● No restrictions for users (OA)
Authentication methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No authentication for users (guest access) ● Manual accounts for administrator and content managers
User interface language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● English (Default) ● German (installed) ● Other languages possible on demand
Navigation and filter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Various entry points and filters

²⁸ <https://lern.link/>

Technical aspect	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Browsing
Indexation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Keywords are used to allow indexation. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Free keywords ○ Fixed keywords <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ DIAMAS vocabulary ■ Areas of activity ■ Stages of publication workflow
Accessibility settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Moodle 4.0 has WCAG 2.1 AA Accessibility compliance. ● Self-assessment of the Living Handbook in preparation
Analytics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● One technically essential cookie: MoodleSession
Licensing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CC Attribution 4.0 International 4.0 on reference entry level, also for referenced sources and materials unless otherwise indicated

A1.2 Security, Access Control, and Data Integrity

Security features	Description
Sitewide URL encryption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) encryption is activated by default on all pages of the website. • The platform’s Secure Sockets Layer (SSL)/ Transport Layer Security (TLS) certificate (Let’s Encrypt) is regularly renewed and automatically managed.
Platform administration account restrictions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Platform administration executed by the service provider lern.link Manager accounts available for users who need to create and manage content or do basic platform configurations
Platform updates (security, Moodle versioning)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular updates by lern.link: Minor updates are rolled out within 14 days after release or faster, if a applicable security issue fix is included. Major updates are performed upon a timeline planned with the customer (customer testing required).
Minor and major updates policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update strategy is based on Long Term Service releases (currently Moodle 4.5) which receive security updates for at least 3 years after the initial release. When security support ends, the platform must be updated to a newer Long Term Support (LTS) version. The upgrade to a new LTS version is planned and performed together with the customer. • Minor updates are rolled out regularly with a timeline based on the issues solved in the individual update.
Backup and recovery procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One daily backup of the entire platform Backups are saved for 7 days and automatically deleted afterwards. • The daily backup is saved on two servers in two different geographical locations.

A2 Toolkit for Living Handbook Editors

This Toolkit is designed to support future editors and content processors as well as content providers in preparing and publishing new references.

Targeted training opportunities and capacity-building workshops will enhance the qualification of contributors, while clear operational guidelines for editors and staff responsible for maintaining the Living Handbook will help establish and sustain it as a community-driven service. To ensure sustainable participation, the scope of community contributions must be clearly defined and limited in terms of expected time and effort.

Accordingly, the following instructions have been developed to streamline editorial workflows, reduce workload, and thereby encourage broader and more consistent participation.

A2.1 Governance

In its role as governance body, the future Editorial Board is responsible for adapting the toolkit to upcoming requirements and for further developing its concept (or its framework). In accordance with this regular adaptation, this Toolkit is to be considered as “living” as the Living Handbook itself. In the further development of the Living Handbook, the Editorial Board will take into account to clearly differentiate the Living Handbook from other EDCH products.

The Editorial Board will be supported by editors invited from various European countries that are willing to provide editorial work to the Living Handbook with a clearly defined number of hours per year. Editors will contribute to keep the Handbook “living” by carrying out the editorial workflow. They will be organised as an editorial team of peers, mutual support will be fostered.

The Living Handbook will be technically maintained under responsibility of the SUB Hamburg. The SUB Hamburg will also support the Editorial Board as well as the Editorial Team, e.g. organising meetings, onboarding new editors and providing manuals for training.

A2.2 Editorial Workflow

This workflow will form the basis for future editorial work. It should be agreed upon by the editorial board and the editors. The intention is to effectively introduce editors to their work through accompanying handouts and training sessions.

Stage	Description	Responsibility
Community Proposals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Call for submissions with thematic categories • Provision of templates for submissions (see Templates for Content Description) 	Editorial Board
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topics are suggested by the community (contact email) • Submissions 	Community
Decision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content review: quality, coherence and relevance 	Editorial Board
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal review: format, accessibility of referenced object, metadata, licensing, etc. 	Editors
Production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check submissions for completeness of information requested (see Templates for Content Description) 	Editors
Editorial Review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proofreading (formal language, style, translations if necessary, see A2.3 Style Guide) 	Editors
Technical Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of reference entries in Moodle based on the reviewed and edited submissions 	Editors
Publication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution is finalised and published. 	Editors

A2.3 Style Guide

The following recommendations are provided to contributors to the Living Handbook and are also used by editors. The guidelines are based on the formal description of the EDCH and are adapted in scope and content.

Category	Topic	Description
General Style and Tone		
	Target audience	Journal editors, publishers, and infrastructure providers in the field of Open Access.
	Tone	Clear, professional, neutral.
	Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusive, accessible. • Active voice over passive voice preferred.
Structure of Contributions		See A2.4 Templates for Content Description
	Title	Descriptive and concise.
	Author(s)/Co-Author(s)	Provide ORCID if available.
	Introduction	A short, target group-specific teaser (500 characters).
	Description	Instruction that provides information on the referenced source and enables users to use your material (up to 500 words).
	Link(s) to the Reference	Persistent Identifier(s) (DOI, ARK...).
	References	Other sources related to the given.
	Further Reading	Provide if available.
	Tags	Based on metadata as requested in A2.4 Templates for Content Description .
	Licensing Note	Default CC-BY 4.0.

Category	Topic	Description
Formatting		
	Headings	Use H2/H3 heading levels.
	Lists	Use bullet points and numbered lists for clarity.
	Highlighting	Use bold terms sparingly.
Technical and Formatting Notes		
	External Links	External links should be hyperlinked with full URLs or DOIs.
	Internal Reference(s)	Refer to internal Handbook entries as “Related Handbook Entries.”
	Tables	Avoid complex table layouts.
	Accessibility	Provide alt-text for all tables and images and follow WCAG 2.0/2.1 accessibility guidelines.
	Open Content	Whenever possible, use tables, graphics and images that you have created yourself or those that are provided under an open license.
Citation Guidelines		
	Citation Style	APA (7th edition) or consistent alternative.
	Source Reference	Always provide full DOI links.
	In-text Citation	(Author, Year) or Author (Year) format. Example <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Bosman et al. (2021) highlighted the importance...</i> • <i>(Wise & Estelle, 2019)</i>
Abbreviation and Terminology		

Category	Topic	Description
	Full Term at First Mention	Spell out full term at first mention, followed by abbreviation in parentheses. Example: Diamond Open Access (Diamond OA)
	DIAMAS Terms/Vocabulary	Use consistent terminology as in DIAMAS Toolsuite (e.g., FOSS, OAI-PMH, JATS XML) (see)
	Glossary	Link to EDCH Glossary (https://toolsuite.diamas.org/glossary) if terms need to be explained. If term is missing, contact EDCH.
Licensing and Openness		
	Contributions and Reused Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All contributions are published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). Ensure correct attribution and licensing of reused content.
Submission and Editorial Process		
	Submission	Submit as described in the Call.
	Quality Assurance	All submissions are subject to review and formatting checks (see A2.2 Editorial Workflow)
	Feedback	Feedback for improving clarity and structure is welcomed by using the contact form.

A2.4 Templates for Content Description

The following templates are used to collect information on project's outcomes in an ongoing process. The collected information is required to create the Living Handbook's entries and metadata to describe them.

The templates are intentionally integrated into the Toolkit to streamline the integration of new content. After consulting with the Editorial Board, it is recommended that these templates be made available to potential contributors via the website, helping to structure submissions and minimise the editors' workload.

A2.4.1 TEMPLATE FOR REFERENCE ENTRIES ON GENERAL CONTENT

Part 1/2

Metadata	Selections to be assigned
Type of material How would you categorise the outcome?	service checklist learning material learning curriculum guideline report plugin Other (please specify):
Format What format is the outcome in?	text format (Portable Document Format (PDF), Word, LaTeX) video software code (PHP, Extensible Markup Language (XML)) webpage (Hypertext Markup Language (HTML))
Target group Who is this outcome made for?	IPSPs IPTPs Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)/Funders Journal Editors Researchers Technical staff Publisher Other (please specify):
Level of experience What expert level would you assign your outcome to?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Basic/beginner ● Advanced

Metadata	Selections to be assigned
<p>Area of activity In which of the following areas of activity does your outcome fit best?</p>	<p>Working with OJS and other editing systems Training and exercise Increasing visibility Networking and communication Guidance and policy management Other (please specify):</p>
<p>Stage of the publication workflow For which of the following phases of the publication process is your outcome designed?</p>	<p>Communication with the author Invitation of the reviewers Managing submissions Peer review management Typesetting and copyediting Digital Object Identifier (DOI) minting Metadata compilation Indexing and dissemination. Creation of outcome formats (HTML, PDF, Electronic Publication (ePub), XML etc.) Publication of outcome formats All None Other (please specify):</p>
<p>Keywords Enter at least four <i>up to seven</i> keywords under which people should be able to find your outcome.</p>	<p>Keyword 1: Keyword 2: Keyword 3: Keyword 4:</p>

Metadata	Selections to be assigned
<p>DIAMAS terms/vocabulary Please assign up to <i>five terms</i> to describe your outcome.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accessibility Copyright Diversity Equity Free and open-source software (FOSS) Funding GDPR Inclusion Indexing/indexation Interoperability Licensing Metadata Metadata and file formats Multilingualism OA Open Science (OS) Governance Peer review Persistent identifiers (PIDs) Preservation Research data Research integrity Sustainability Transparency Visibility

Part 2/2

Description of the training
Title Name of the outcome
Lead author(s) Name(s) of lead author(s)
Contributor(s) Anyone who contributes to the described outcome.
Introduction Short, target group-specific teaser (500 characters) that makes users want to use the outcome, with a focus on what problem the outcome solves.
Description A short instruction manual that provides information and enables the user to use your outcome. Also inform the users what the benefits of using the outcome are. (up to 500 words)
Link(s) to the outcome
References Is there other outcome of the project or by third parties that is connected to yours? In what way is it connected?
Further reading
The entry is available with a CC BY 4.0 licence (https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

A2.4.2 TEMPLATE FOR REFERENCE ENTRIES ON TRAINING MATERIALS

Part 1/2

Metadata	Selections to be assigned
<p>Type of material How would you categorise the training material?</p>	<p>hand-out instruction checklist self-paced course educational game Other (please specify):</p>
<p>Format What format are the training materials provided in? (Tick all that apply.)</p>	<p>text format Please specify: ... slides video software code Please specify: ... webpage (HTML) software installation / sandbox Other (please specify):</p>
<p>Reusable Curriculum for Upskilling Training Please indicate if (or if not) your material can be related to the thematic blocks of the curriculum.</p>	<p>Publishing systems and their features (Introduction to common publishing systems / Advanced use of publishing systems / XML publishing workflows) Metadata I: quality through standards (Introduction to metadata / Metadata standards / Metadata harvesting, depositing and export / Controlled vocabularies) Metadata II: identifiers (Introduction to IDs, PIDs and metadata standards / Identifier systems) Metadata III: licensing, OA and self-archiving policy (Introduction to OA models and licence types / Journal's self-archiving policy / Setting up the publishing system) Content accessibility (Content provisioning / Content harvesting and indexing / Content depositing and export / Content long-term archiving) <i>No relation given to the above-mentioned thematic blocks</i></p>

Metadata	Selections to be assigned
<p>Target group Who is this outcome made for?</p>	<p>Researchers Journal Editors IPSPs IPTPs RPOs Technical staff Publishers Other (please specify):</p>
<p>Level of experience What expert level would you assign your outcome to?</p>	<p>Basic/beginner Advanced</p>
<p>Keywords Enter at least four <i>up to seven</i> keywords that describe the training material/under which people should be able to find it</p>	<p>Keyword 1: Keyword 2: Keyword 3: Keyword 4:</p>
<p>DIAMAS terms/vocabulary Please assign up to <i>five terms</i> to describe your outcome.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Accessibility ● Copyright ● Diversity ● Equity ● FOSS ● Funding ● GDPR ● Inclusion ● Indexing/indexation ● Interoperability ● Licensing ● Metadata ● Metadata and file formats ● Multilingualism ● OA ● OS ● Governance ● Peer review ● PIDs ● Preservation ● Research data ● Research integrity ● Sustainability ● Transparency

Metadata	Selections to be assigned
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><li data-bbox="756 304 903 331">• Visibility

Part 2/2

Description of the training
Title Name of the training material
Creator(s) Name(s) of creator(s)
Contributor(s) Anyone who contributes to the described training material
Version / Date Version of training material and the date of its creation
Introduction A short, target group-specific teaser (500 characters), what the training material is about
Learning target(s) Brief statement what skills and abilities learners should have at the end of a learning process.
Description Short instruction manual that provides information and enables users to use your material. enefits for the users (up to 500 words)
Link(s) to the training material(s)
License(s) of the training material(s)
Further reading
The entry is available with a CC BY 4.0 license (https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

A3 Deliverables and Milestones for the Living Handbook

This is the result of the content identification as described in [3.4.1 Content Identification](#).

Inclusion in the Living Handbook	Title of the Entry	Description
Reusable curriculum for upskilling training	Reusable curriculum for upskilling training	Set-up of a common helpdesk system and connection with all service providers
Closing Gaps – Enabling Community Transformation	Technical gap analysis and high-level community transition plans	Capturing all training activities and materials and making them accessible
Best Practices and Technical Standards in Publishing	Report on standards for best publishing practices and basic technical standards	Interoperability framework aligned with DIAMAS project outcomes
OA Journals & Platforms: Challenges and Support Measures	Report on challenges and help measures faced by OA journals and platforms	Identification of primary technical challenges and gaps for OA journals
Implementing Technical Standards: Training & Self-Assessment Toolkit	Training Materials on Implementing Technical Standards and Self-Assessment Toolkit	Toolkit to comply with the agreed interoperability framework
OJS Improvements: Expanding Core Functionality & Usability	OJS core feature enhancements	New core features for OJS created in T4.1 and T4.3
Journal Article Tag Suite (JATS) XML Interoperability: Connecting OJS and Lodel	Plugins to enable JATS XML-based interoperability between OJS and Lodel	Requirements analysis for interoperability between publishing frameworks
Upgrade Toolkit: Best Practices for OJS and Lodel	Deployment and upgrading toolkits and recommendations for OJS and Lodel	State-of-the-art implementation and operation of journal software
Technical Requirements of Aggregators: Scalable Documentation	Scalable and adjustable documentation of how to understand the aggregators' technical requirements	Inventory of technical requirements for publication aggregators
DDH	DDH is ready for interoperability and use	DDH available, handed over to WP7 for exploitation to start

Inclusion in the Living Handbook	Title of the Entry	Description
"DDH: Step-by-Step Onboarding for IPTP, IPSP & Journals	Documentation and guidelines on how to onboard IPTP, IPSP, journals, content, tools to the DDH	Supporting journal publishing technology for RPOs and small units
DISCO Plugin: Self-Assessment Tool for Visibility in Diamond OA	DISCO Plugin and Blueprint Adjusted and Approved by IPSP Community	Tool to self-assess visibility via the CRAFT-OA tooling suite
Connecting OJS with OpenAIRE: Automated Metadata Sharing	OJS connector for OpenAIRE Research Graph	Updating the OJS plugin for OpenAIRE metadata aggregation
OJS Plugin for EOSC Interoperability: Enhancing Research Product Publishing	OJS plugin for the EOSC Interoperability Framework on Research Product Publishing	Aligning with the EOSC Interoperability Framework on Research Product Publishing
OJS Plugins for EOSC Catalogue Feedback Integration	OJS plugins for integrating feedback from EOSC catalogue practices	Integrating feedback from EOSC catalog practices
Guidelines for Publishers: Managing and Integrating Research Supporting Data	Recommendations for publishers for handling research supporting data	Guidelines for handling research supporting data
Federated Trust & Identity (T&I) Best Practices for Diamond OA: Requirements, Architecture & Guidelines	Federated Trust and Identity (T&I) technical requirements, architecture and best practices	Definition of T&I best practices for Diamond OA journal partners
Dashboard service released in OpenAIRE infrastructure	OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard Service	Dashboard service released in OpenAIRE infrastructure
IPTP Network Management Toolkit for Scholarly Open Access Publishing	Toolkit for IPTP network	Toolkit for managing the IPTP network for scholarly Open Access publishing services

A4 SWOT Analyses for the Use of Software for the Living Handbook

A4.1 Moodle

SWOT Category	Analysis
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Built for e-learning: Moodle is designed for managing courses and learning content, making it ideal for interactive training within the handbook.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● User management and roles: Offers a robust system for managing users with different permissions (e.g., authors, editors, reviewers).
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open source: Moodle is free to use and highly customisable, with a large library of plugins for added functionality.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Interactive tools: Moodle supports quizzes, assignments, forums, and multimedia, which can enhance a Living Handbook by adding interactivity.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Multilingual support: Built-in support for multiple languages makes it accessible to a global audience.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mobile-friendly: Moodle provides a mobile app, allowing users to access the handbook on the go.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scalable: Can handle a large number of users and content, making it suitable for both small and large handbooks.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Community support: A large, active open-source community that contributes to plugins, updates, and documentation.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Tracking and reporting: Moodle provides detailed analytics on user engagement, activity, and progress, allowing authors to monitor usage trends.
	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Limited content structure: Moodle's structure is course-based, which may not be as flexible for complex documentation as systems like Drupal. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Customization requires technical skills: While open source, extensive customization and plugin management may require technical expertise. 	

SWOT Category	Analysis
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No built-in version control for content: Moodle does not offer robust version control for managing frequent content updates and revisions.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No peer review system: Lacks a formal peer review workflow, which is essential for collaborative content creation in some handbooks.
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Integration with external systems: Moodle can be integrated with platforms like Drupal or OJS to manage complex content and metadata.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adding training features: Ideal for Living Handbooks that include training modules, certifications, or interactive learning components.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Custom plugins: Opportunity to develop or install plugins that add features like metadata management or DOI integration.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Growing user base: As online learning becomes more prevalent, there's a growing demand for platforms like Moodle to deliver interactive learning content within handbooks.
Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of advanced content management: Moodle's course-based structure may become limiting for more complex handbooks or those needing frequent updates.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Dependency on plugins: Heavy reliance on third-party plugins could lead to compatibility issues and increase maintenance complexity.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Security risks: As with any open-source platform, security vulnerabilities require constant monitoring and updates to prevent breaches.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scaling performance: While scalable, performance may degrade as the number of users or the size of content grows, requiring optimization.

A4.2 Drupal

SWOT Category	Analysis
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Highly customizable: Drupal allows creating custom content types, taxonomies, and flexible structures.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Metadata and standards support: Supports standards like Dublin Core, essential for academic content.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Robust permission system: Fine-grained control over user roles and permissions for collaborative work.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Multilingual capabilities: Built-in support for multiple languages, ideal for global reach.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scalability: Suitable for large-scale projects with high volumes of content and users.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open source: No licensing costs, and a large range of modules for additional functionality.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strong community: Active community contributes to ongoing development, support, and security.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Powerful search: Built-in search with extensive filtering options to find and categorize content.
Weaknesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Steep learning curve: Drupal’s complexity makes it difficult for non-technical users to manage.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High maintenance: Setup and customization require experienced developers, increasing long-term costs.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Overkill for simple projects: For smaller handbooks, Drupal might be unnecessarily complex.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Performance issues: May require optimization to handle large sites efficiently.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Limited collaboration tools: Lacks real-time collaboration features without additional modules.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Resource-intensive: Requires more server resources, which can increase hosting costs.
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Integration with other systems: Drupal can be integrated with Moodle or other LMS for learning features.

SWOT Category	Analysis
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Growth potential: As the handbook grows, Drupal can scale without significant reconfiguration.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Custom workflows: Tailored workflows can be created for content review, updates, and publishing.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Community-driven innovation: Ongoing contributions from the Drupal community may provide new tools and functionalities.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● New technologies: Drupal can adapt to emerging web technologies like APIs and AI tools for content management.
Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High development costs: Extensive customization and updates may require significant investment.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Compatibility issues: Major updates could lead to compatibility problems with custom modules and themes.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Security vulnerabilities: Like any open-source system, it requires constant attention to security updates.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Technological obsolescence: As technologies evolve, Drupal modules or practices may become outdated, requiring additional updates.

A4.3 Comparison of Software (Moodle / Drupal)

Criteria	Moodle	Drupal
Ease of Use	Moodle is easy to use for non-technical users, with an intuitive interface for managing content.	Drupal has a steep learning curve and requires technical expertise for setup and management.
Cost and Customization	Open-source and cost-effective, Moodle has a large repository of free plugins that require little to no development effort for common features.	While also open-source, Drupal customization is costly, requiring developers for advanced functionalities and complex configurations.
Learning and Training Tools	Built-in support for quizzes, certifications, learning paths , and other e-learning tools.	Lacks native learning management features; would need external tools or heavy customization for similar functionality.
Maintenance	Moodle has lower maintenance requirements , with fewer updates and less technical overhead.	Drupal needs regular updates , module compatibility checks, and ongoing technical maintenance, which can be resource-intensive.
Mobile-Friendly	Moodle offers a mobile app and is responsive out of the box, making content easily accessible across all devices.	While responsive, Drupal’s mobile experience may require additional customisation for optimal performance.
Interactivity and Engagement	Moodle supports forums, real-time collaboration , and interactive tools such as quizzes, which enhance user engagement.	Drupal lacks out-of-the-box interactive features like quizzes and forums, requiring custom modules to add interactivity.
Multilingual Support	Moodle natively supports multiple languages with an easy-to-manage interface for translation.	Drupal also supports multilingual content but often requires more complex configuration and module setup for optimal functionality.
Scalability and Flexibility	Moodle can handle a large number of users and content without becoming overly complex or requiring significant technical overhead.	Drupal is highly scalable but comes with increased complexity , requiring more technical resources to manage as the system grows.

Criteria	Moodle	Drupal
Integration Options	Moodle can integrate seamlessly with other platforms, including Drupal , using LTI or API connections .	Drupal can integrate with external systems but often requires custom development and complex integrations to function smoothly.
Target Audience	Ideal for educational and training-focused handbooks , Moodle provides tools for user certification and progress tracking .	Drupal is more suited for content-heavy websites with complex structures but is overkill for simple handbooks focused on education and training.
Community Support	Moodle has a strong, active community dedicated to education, with a focus on developing tools for learning and training .	Drupal's community is broad but less focused on educational tools , making it harder to find specific learning management solutions.